

Temperature performance of the lithium/O₂ battery^ψ

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The lithium-oxygen battery utilizing non-aqueous electrolyte demonstrates a high specific energy and limited rechargability^{1,2}. The main discharge products have been characterized and the effect of electrolyte properties on cell performance have been demonstrated. This paper describes the temperature performance of a lithium-oxygen battery using non-aqueous electrolyte and correlates this to changes in electrolyte viscosity with temperature. This paper presents the temperature performance of our baseline Li-O₂ cell in the temperature range from -30°C to +40°C at discharge rates from 0.5 to 0.05 mA/cm².

The discharge reactions for the non-aqueous Li-O₂ cell can be written as :

The rate behavior of the Li-O₂ cell has been shown to depend on the transport of oxygen into the carbon cathode through the organic electrolyte permeating the cathode³. The transport of oxygen into the cathode should be affected by changes in temperature as gas solubility decreases with increasing temperature for most gases⁴ in common liquids and gas diffusion generally increases with increasing temperature⁵. The product of the oxygen solubility and the oxygen diffusion coefficient will be proportional to the flux of oxygen into the carbon cathode. To evaluate whether changes in gas solubility or gas diffusion dominate performance, we evaluated our baseline Li-O₂ cell in the temperature range from -30°C to +40°C at discharge rates from 0.05 to 0.5 mA/cm². In this paper we will present the results of those studies.

Results

Table 1 shows the specific capacity of our baseline cell over the range of rates and temperatures tested with Fig. 1 showing the same data graphically with error bars included. Fig. 2 shows several voltage versus discharge curves at the 0.1 mA/cm² rate for various temperatures. The results for discharge at 20°C correspond well with our previous results obtained for discharge at ambient temperature³. Fig. 1 shows that the specific capacity of

Table 1. Specific capacity of Super P (mAh/g) as a function of temperature and discharge rate

Temp. (°C)	Rate of discharge (mA/cm ²)			
	0.05	0.1	0.2	0.5
-30	429	233	0	0
-20	521	426	199	42
0	703	482	340	140
20	1468	961	637	240
40	2193	1894	1704	446

Fig. 1. Specific capacity of Super P (mAh/g) as a function of temperature at various discharge rates.

the Li/O₂ system has a strong dependence on temperature. The increase in specific capacity with increasing temperature appears linear at 0.5 mA/cm² and exponential at the low discharge rate of 0.05 mA/cm². On aver-

^ψDedicated to Professor H. C. Gaur on his 80th birthday.

Fig. 2. Voltage versus specific capacity of Super P (mAh/g) at 0.1 mA/cm² as a function of temperature.

age, the capacity doubles for each 20°C rise in temperature. The upper limit in capacity for these Super P cathodes as prepared is typically 2000 mAh/g. This capacity is approached at 40°C at the 0.2 mA/cm² discharge rate.

Fig. 3 shows the electrolyte viscosity (η) in centipoises as a function of temperature. The relationship between diffusion coefficient (D), temperature (T) and viscosity (η) is described using the Stokes-Einstein relation

$$D = \frac{kT}{6\pi\eta a}$$

where k is the Boltzmann constant and a is the effective hydrodynamic radius of O₂. If we use the O₂ bond length of 121 pm for the hydrodynamic radius a , we can calculate a diffusion coefficient for O₂ in 1 M LiPF₆ PC : DME (1 : 1 w/w) of 5.5×10^{-6} cm²/s at 20°C. This is in good agreement with O₂ diffusion in other organic solvents at 20°C. The diffusion coefficient calculated from -35°C to 45°C is shown in Fig. 4. The change in diffu-

Fig. 3. Viscosity versus temperature of 1 M LiPF₆ PC : DME (1 : 1) electrolyte.

sion coefficient shows a weak activated behavior and an activation energy of 66 cal/mol.

Fig. 4. Diffusion coefficient of O₂ versus temperature in 1 M LiPF₆ PC : DME (1 : 1) electrolyte.

The exponential dependence of the diffusion coefficient on temperature appears to be the dominating factor influencing discharge capacity. The total discharge capacity for a particular rate and temperature will not follow exactly the changes in electrolyte viscosity or oxygen solubility due to other factors such as changes in electrode porosity as discharge proceeds and by the nature of the oxygen concentration gradient set up in the carbon electrode as discharge takes place. The rapid increase in discharge capacity at all rates with temperature indicates that the diffusion coefficient of oxygen in electrolyte dominates performance and that any decrease in oxygen solubility with rising temperature does not appear to be significant.

Several anomalies were seen in the voltage profiles of cells discharged at 40°C. Fig. 2 shows an increase in voltage occurring at 500 mAh/g and lasting until 1500 mAh/g. This increase in voltage as discharge occurs might be traced to the presence of HF or water in the electrolyte from the decomposition of LiPF₆ at elevated temperature. The rising voltage would indicate that more HF or water is being generated over time. A simpler explanation could be that there is inherent instability in the 1 M LiPF₆ PC : DME (1 : 1 w/w) electrolyte towards Li₂O₂ and that this instability becomes apparent at elevated temperatures. This would be similar to the instability of a similar electrolyte 1 M LiPF₆ PC : DEC (1 : 1 w/w) at room temperature³. Both possibilities could lead to a higher discharge capacity and a higher discharge voltage.

Experimental

Carbon cathodes were prepared by paste coating a mixture of emulsified polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) and

Super P carbon black onto aluminum grids. The finished cathodes were 90% Super P and 10% PTFE with a thickness of 0.065–0.075 cm. Cathodes were dried under vacuum at 105°C for 2 h before cell assembly. Cells were assembled by placing a 10 cm² lithium anode on a polypropylene block, with a non-woven separator and a 5 cm² cathode placed upon that. The cathode/separator/anode assembly was bound to the polypropylene block using insulated copper wires. Cells were placed in foil laminate pouches and 6 g of electrolyte were added. 150 ml of O₂ was then sealed into the pouch. Cell impedance was recorded after a minimum one-hour rest. Cells were placed in a temperature controlled chamber, allowed to soak at temperature for 3 h, and were then discharged at rates from 0.05 to 0.5 mA/cm² to a 2 V cutoff. Discharge capacities were normalized to the weight of carbon in the cathode and reported as specific capacity of Super P.

The baseline electrolyte for our study was 1 M LiPF₆ in PC : DME (1 : 1 w/w). LiPF₆ electrolytes were prepared from Ferro Corporation electrolyte grade solvents determined to contain less than 20 ppm water by Karl Fisher titration. Stella Chemifa LiPF₆ was used as received. Electrolyte was prepared in a glovebox with <5 ppm O₂ and <1 ppm water.

Viscosity measurements were carried out using a Brookfield DV-II viscometer with UL adapter for low viscosity liquids. Temperature was controlled using an oil bath for above ambient measurements and a heptane bath in a temperature chamber for below ambient temperature. Measurements were carried out at a spindle

speed of either 60 rpm (shear rate of 73.38 s⁻¹) or 30 rpm (shear rate of 36.69 s⁻¹).

Conclusions :

The performance of our baseline Li-O₂ cell is strongly influenced by temperature. This dependence appears to result from the strong effect temperature has on the diffusion of oxygen through the electrolyte. The elevated temperature performance shows a voltage anomaly at low rates that suggests either instability of LiPF₆ salt or instability of the 1 M LiPF₆ PC : DME electrolyte towards Li₂O₂. Further measurements will be required to separate the effects of oxygen solubility from oxygen diffusion. The effect temperature has on discharge kinetics should also be studied. Temperature performance at or below 0°C could be improved by reformulating the electrolyte to increase oxygen diffusion and oxygen solubility.

References

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